

The influence of Consumers' Purchase intention on Smart Wearable Device: A study of Consumers in East China

Chen Wei

Abstract

In order to better analyze the influencing factors of consumers' purchase intention of smart wearable devices, this paper uses the technology acceptance model as the theoretical basis, and selects the factors that may have a greater impact on the purchase intention of smart wearable devices as the investigation project. By constructing a theoretical analysis model of consumers' purchase intention of smart wearable devices, interpret the relationship between the key variables of smart wearable devices and the influence of consumers' purchase intention, verify the credibility of various assumptions, and propose the development path of China's smart wearable industry based on the research and analysis results. Specifically, the research contents include the following: (1) According to relevant theories and literature analysis, screen out the influencing factors that affect the usefulness and ease of use of smart wearable devices, and under the framework of the technology acceptance model, analyze the explanatory relationship of the influencing factors that affect consumers to purchase smart wearable devices from two aspects: perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness. (2) With the help of investigation and statistical analysis, the correlation between independent variables and dependent variables that affect the purchase intention of smart wearable devices is discussed. (3) Starting from the personal characteristic attributes of consumers such as age, gender, educational background and income level, the differences between the personal characteristic attributes of consumers and the purchase intention of consumers of smart wearable devices are discussed. The path relationship between independent variables and dependent variables shows that the theoretical analysis model of the purchase intention of smart wearable device consumers constructed in this paper can better analyze the internal influence of the factors affecting the purchase intention of smart wearable device consumers, and help smart wearable device manufacturers and intermediate service providers better understand the key factors affecting the purchase intention of smart wearable device consumers, and guide their product development and marketing activities.

IJSB

Accepted 12 May 2021

Published 16 May 2021

DOI: 0.5281/zenodo.4765601

Keywords: *Smart wearable device, Technology acceptance model, Perceived ease of use, Perceived usefulness, Purchase intention.*

About Author (s)

Chen Wei, Asia Metropolitan University, Malaysia.

INTRODUCTION

Industry Background of Smart Wearable Devices

With the increasing commercial use of mass technology products, especially the opening of 5G high-speed network applications, more and more innovative technology products are used by consumers, and the application research of technology acceptance models will return to the public's vision in the future. However, the biggest problem in the application of new technologies is whether new technology products can be accepted and used by consumers. Therefore, new research on technology acceptance models in various fields has become a hot topic in management. Smart wearable device is a portable device that is worn directly on the body or integrated into the user's clothes or accessories. It is not only a hardware device, but also realizes powerful functions through software support, data interaction and cloud interaction. Wearable device will bring great changes to our life and perception. The concept of smart wearable devices was first put forward by foreign scholars in the 1960s. Limited by the level of science and technology at that time, the research stayed on the theory and form of smart wearable devices. In the 21st century, with the rapid development of technology, smart wearable devices began to show their unique charm and magical functions to people. Especially since 2005, the concept of smart wearable devices has continued to be hot. Some famous foreign universities, such as Massachusetts Institute of Technology and Stanford University, have set up research groups and laboratories one after another to invest a lot of money every year to explore this field. Some well-known domestic enterprises, such as Ali, Baidu, Huawei and Xiaomi, have also invested heavily in the industry and carried out a number of research and development projects on smart wearable devices. As one of the inventions and expansions of intelligent technology closely related to human life, the emergence and extensive expansion of smart wearable devices are changing the way of human life. In 2006, Nike and Apple teamed up to launch the Nike + iPod - a sports kit that combines a portable music player with a smart pedometer, marking the first step in mobile health tracking of wearables. In 2009, Fitbit launched its first product, the Fitbit Tracker, a thumb-sized "pedometer" that quickly set off an exercise and fitness craze in North America. In 2012, the smart wearable industry entered the era of rapid development in which a hundred flowers bloom and a hundred schools of thought contend, attracting global attention to the smart wearable industry. After 2014, the world's major companies entered the stadium, accelerating the landing of wearable devices in various industries. From 2014 to 2018, Google launched an Android Wear system specially used in wearable devices. Xiaomi and Huami jointly launched the "Mi Band" and Apple launched the Apple Watch, which provides more in-depth application services in sports and health scenes and provides more powerful heart rate tracking functions. In 2018, Apple Watch intensified its exploration in the health field, and its electrocardiogram (ECG) intelligent monitoring product was certified by the U.S. Food and Drug Administration. In the domestic market, Huami Technology has followed Apple's footsteps with the introduction of a new watch series AMAZFIT, which enhanced exercise and health functions and can monitor heart rate changes around the clock. In addition, in the health field, the smart watch Huawei Watch GT series is equipped with , namely TruSeen 3.0 heart rate monitoring function to monitor heart rate and sleep quality in real time. At present, the shipments of smart wearable products in the Chinese market have entered a period of rapid development. Especially under the background of the 2020 epidemic, smart wearable products have shown their technological advantages in the control of home isolation personnel and the health intelligent monitoring of the left-behind elderly, helping to fight the epidemic and giving smart wearable products a special historical mission. With the gradual popularization of 5G networks, the research and development and promotion of smart wearable devices in China has entered a period of rapid upsurge. IDC's "China Wearable Device Market Quarterly Tracking Report (Third Quarter in 2019)" shows

that China's wearable device market shipped 27.15 million units in the third quarter of 2019, up 45.2% year-on-year. Among them, the largest increase was in smart bracelets, smart watches and other devices, with an increase of 86.3%. Judging from the figures, China's smart wearable device market is still a blue sea, and the market scale still has a lot of room for improvement. In the next five years, the production and demand of China's smart wearable devices will further increase, and China's smart wearable market has become an emerging market force that cannot be ignored. However, the characteristics of people's consumption demand for smart wearable devices and the key influencing factors for consumers to purchase smart wearable devices are urgent issues for industrial development.

Description of research questions

The Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) is proposed based on the theory of reasoned behavior (TRA). It is widely used in information system research and can help understand people's cognition or acceptance of information technology. Extensive empirical research has been carried out abroad, but its application in China is less and its scope is limited. Based on the TAM model theory, this paper discusses the consumer's attitude towards smart wearable devices, their demand and the influencing factors of their selection system, evaluates the consumer's acceptance of smart wearable devices, and establish a theoretical model of the factors influencing consumers' acceptance of smart wearable devices, and then put forward specific suggestions, hoping to provide some references for the development and management of China's smart wearable industry. Based on this, the research questions in this paper are as follows:

Question 1: What are the main variables that affect the ease of use of smart wearable devices and what are the main variables that affect the usefulness of smart wearable devices? Into which explanatory factors can these variables be classified, and what is the degree of explanation of the survey question items of these influencing factors on the original variables?

Question 2: Do consumers' personal characteristic attributes such as gender, age, educational background, income status and other factors affect their willingness to purchase and use smart wearable devices, and do these personal characteristic attributes have significant differences in their willingness to purchase smart wearable devices?

Research Objectives

To better analyze the influencing factors of consumers' purchase intention of smart wearable devices, this paper uses the technology acceptance model as the theoretical basis, and selects the factors that may have a greater impact on the purchase intention of smart wearable devices as the investigation project. By constructing a theoretical analysis model of consumers' purchase intention of smart wearable devices, interpret the relationship between the key variables of smart wearable devices and the influence of consumers' purchase intention, verify the credibility of various hypotheses, and propose the development path of China's smart wearable industry based on the research and analysis results. Specifically, the research objectives include the following:

Research Objective 1: To investigate the degree of explanation of the variance of the original variables by the questioned items. According to relevant theories and literature analysis, various influencing variables that affect consumers' purchase of smart wearable devices are screened out, an analysis survey scale of various variables is constructed, and the explanatory ability of various survey items on the purchase intention of smart wearable devices to the original variables is discussed, which provides support for completing the analysis of smart wearable devices.

Research Objective 2: Differential analysis of consumer purchase intention. Starting from the characteristic attributes of consumers, the differences between the personal characteristic attributes of consumers such as gender, age, educational background, income status and the purchase intention of smart wearable device consumers are discussed.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Consumer Purchase Intention

Purchase intention refers to whether a consumer is willing to buy a product at a balanced market price under the condition that the consumer's monetary income is established. Consumer purchase intention refers to the probability that the consumer is willing to take a specific purchase behavior.

Preliminary study

Mitchell(1999) believed that the consumer's attitude towards a certain product or brand, combined with the effect of external factors, constitutes the consumer's purchase intention. The purchase intention can be regarded as the subjective tendency of consumers to choose specific products, and has been proved to be an important indicator for predicting consumer behavior. Juliet, B. (2010) argues that purchase intention refers to the subjective probability or likelihood that a consumer will purchase a particular product, while some scholars argue that purchase intention is the consumer's purchase plan for a particular good. Zhou (2020) considered purchase intention as the possibility of consumers to buy the product, and he constructed a research model and proposed hypotheses by studying the theory based on technology acceptance model, then designed and collected questionnaires and tested them using SPSS and Amos statistical software, and finally constructed a structural equation model path diagram. The empirical results enrich the theoretical results and practical value of the research on the influence of consumers' purchase intention. Wang and Gao (2020) believe that the purchase intention is a psychological consultant for consumers to buy goods suitable for their own needs, a manifestation of consumer psychology and a prelude to purchase behavior. Based on the stimulus-organism-response theory, he studied the influence of individual consumer behavior characteristics on purchase intention in the online shopping environment by influencing consumers' cognition, experience and psychological characteristics. Research shows that information involvement, network closeness and individual innovation have significant positive effects on purchase intention, while perceived risk has significant negative effects on purchase intention. Perceived risk is divided into functional risk and emotional risk. Individual innovation plays a regulatory role in the influence path of functional risk and emotional risk on purchase intention, and functional risk and emotional risk play a part mediating role in the overall model. Hu, Shi, Yu, Mao, et al. (2021) constructed an extended technology acceptance model by introducing three potential variables: perceived risk, service quality and social impact. Then, the latent variables, personal socio-economic attribute variables and travel mode attribute variables of the extended technology acceptance model are integrated into multiple Logit models, a hybrid selection model is constructed, and the probability of users choosing to share self-driving cars to travel is used to measure the user's purchase intention of using shared self-driving cars.

Software and Hardware Design of Smart Devices

The software of smart device is a logical product, which is essentially different from hardware products. Hardware is a visible and tangible physical component or device. When developing hardware products, people's creative activities are manifested in transforming raw materials into tangible physical products. Software products exist in the form of programs and documents, and their role is reflected by running on computers. The design of smart wearable

products includes the design of software and hardware functional modules of smart wearable devices. Whether the design of smart wearable products meets the needs of consumers is the main basis for consumers to be willing to purchase and try to use smart wearable devices. The design of software and hardware functional modules of smart wearable devices mainly includes the quality level of functions and performance of smart wearable products produced by research and development and production enterprises according to the needs of market consumers. If the quality is good, the evaluation of consumers' perceived usability and perceived usefulness will be improved. At the same time, their willingness to purchase will be improved, and the possibility of final purchase behavior will be higher.

Previous research on the relationship with independent variables

According to research by Wang, Liang, Fan, Deng, et al. (2017), the coexistence of software and hardware devices is the biggest difference between intelligent devices and traditional products. To this end, based on the technology acceptance model (TAM) and the characteristics of consumers' online car-booking travel behavior, he constructed a theoretical model of the influencing factors of consumers' online car-booking travel, and completed the influencing factors of online car-booking software through sample surveys. The results show that: subjective norms, usage feelings, and software design level have an impact on perceived usefulness, of which perceived price level negatively affects perceived usefulness; self-efficacy, perceived external control, and perceived pleasure have a positive impact on perceived usability; perceived usability positively affects perceived usefulness; perceived usability and perceived usefulness positively affect users' travel intentions. Huang (2019) extends and proposes the Senior Technology Acceptance Model (STAM) on the basis of the theory of technology acceptance model, and proposes the importance of software to smart device. He developed a structured questionnaire based on the variables of the new technology acceptance model, conducted research and interviews to understand the attitudes and intentions of the elderly towards smart home appliances, summarized the problems of using smart home appliances among the elderly, and collected relevant statistical data. He used the Structural Equation Model (SEM) to analyze the effects of four core elements of product design: product function, software function design, product appearance, and interaction interface on perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, perceived pleasure, perceived safety, behavioral intention, and system use. Based on the technology acceptance model, Wei Ling and Guo Xinyue (2020) regarded users' willingness to continuously use knowledge payment platforms as a performance under the stimulus-organism-response (S-O-R) model, and based on the usability and convenience of software design, proposed that perceived value, immersion experience, perceived usefulness, and perceived ease of use significantly influenced consumers' willingness to continuously use, and then, they put forward relevant suggestions for platform operators based on this conclusion.

Theory of Reasoned Action comes from social psychology and is considered as one of the most basic and influential theories to study cognitive behavior. This theory fully illustrates the influence of motivation and information on behavior. This model can be regarded as a deliberate process model, because they represent the behavioral decisions made by individuals after careful consideration based on available information. This theory suggests that people tend to follow a reasoned action that enables them to obtain favorable outcomes and to conform to others. It arose from a study of mental processes done by Feishbein and was discovered by Feishbein when he analyzed the failure of attitudes to predict behavior. Due to the openness and conciseness of TRA, it is believed that it can further deepen the research or be added other predictive variables, and many scholars have conducted extensive research on it. According to the different research topics and emphases, these existing TRA

expansion studies can be classified into three categories: theoretical deepening research on the perfection of TRA theory itself; expansion research on the applicability of TRA with situational variables; and model expansion research that incorporates new variables into TRA models. The significance of this theory lies in that it illustrates two basic hypotheses: first, attitude and subjective norms are mediating variables that affect behavior tendency by other variables; second, behavior intention is a mediating variable that affects behavior by attitude and subjective norms. Some researchers believe that adding other structures to the TRA model will reduce the refinement of the TRA model. Therefore, a common extension study is to further study the variables contained in the TRA. These studies mainly include three types, namely, in-depth research on the attitude toward behavior dimension, in-depth research on the subjective norm dimension, and in-depth research on attitude toward behaviors, which are hot spot in the extension study of TRA itself. From the existing studies, there are two main types of studies that focus on the division of attitude toward behaviors.

METHODOLOGY

Objectives of investigation

1. With the help of investigation and analysis, analyze the influence factors and relationships of consumers using smart wearable products from two aspects of perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness;
2. Verify the authenticity of the 13 basic hypotheses proposed in this paper, and complete the key factors affecting the promotion and application of smart wearable products with empirical analysis.

Questionnaire Design

The design of smart wearable products includes the design of software and hardware functional modules of smart wearable devices. Whether the design of smart wearable products meets the needs of consumers is the main basis for consumers to be willing to purchase and try to use smart wearable devices. As a new high-tech intelligent product, it is very important for consumers to fully understand the functional characteristics and usage methods of smart wearable products in the shortest possible time. With the help of publicity, promotion and education and training on the service functions of smart wearable devices, consumers' awareness of smart wearable device software can be improved, thus enhancing consumers' willingness to purchase smart wearable devices. In order to complete the above analysis, this study intends to complete the collection of required data through questionnaire survey. The design of questionnaire items mainly refers to the design description of relevant questionnaires, and is compiled according to the research purpose and research hypotheses. The questionnaire is divided into five parts, The first part is the investigation of the influence of smart wearable product design, publicity and education and consumer service on consumers' perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness; The second part is the investigation of the influence of consumers' subjective norms, innovation characteristics and perceived risks on their perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness; The third part is the investigation of perceived ease of use to perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness to consumers' intention to use; The fourth part is a survey to understand consumers' intention to use smart wearable products, thereby completing the analysis of consumers' intention to use smart wearable products and the relationship between various factors. The fifth part is the personal data of consumers, including four questions such as gender, age, educational background and income level.

Population / Sampling / Unit of Analysis

According to the previous description, consumers' attitude towards smart wearable devices has a great influence on their purchase intention. Previous scholars have applied the technology acceptance model to a very large number of research areas, and this paper is mainly based on previous studies, with modifications made in this specific context to fit the purpose of the study, so the scale design mainly refers to the studies of Davis (1986), Ajzen (2006), and others, who provide more detailed measurement scales.

Reliability and validity test scheme

In this study, after the completion of the design of the first draft of the questionnaire and before the formal test, in order to understand whether the questionnaire design is perfect and to test the reliability of the questionnaire, to avoid semantic problems in the content of the questionnaire, which leads the respondents to misunderstand the meaning of the questionnaire and answer the questionnaire by mistake, the questionnaire will be pre-tested in advance and the non-significant items will be deleted. This study mainly implements reliability analysis in the process of questionnaire pre-test analysis. Cronbach's alpha is used to measure the consistency and stability of the entire questionnaire item. The higher the number of alpha coefficients, the higher the internal consistency of the scale. According to Nunnally, reliability above 0.7 is considered reliable; Cuieford believes that Cronbach's alpha greater than 0.7 is considered as high reliability, between 0.7 and 0.35 is considered as fair reliability, and less than 0.35 is considered as low reliability and should be rejected. Based on the pre-test items of the questionnaire, the formal questionnaire was distributed after appropriate revision. In order to discuss the influence of survey items on intention to use, this study conducts factor analysis for perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, software design, publicity and education, consumer service, subjective norms, innovation characteristics, perceived risks and purchase intentions. Before conducting factor analysis, the statistical values were first tested with the help of KMO test to determine the suitability of the sample information for factor analysis in this study.

Data collecting process

Sample source

This study focuses on consumers in East China as the survey target. The intention to use smart wearable devices such as smart bracelet products is the survey content, and the comprehensive discussion of consumers' intention to use smart wearable products and its influencing factors is completed. The survey sites are generally chosen from electronic shopping centers, electronic product counters in large commercial buildings, and specialized stores of related brands.

Investigation arrangements

This study mainly takes the first-tier and second-tier urban residents in East China as the measurement objects. Due to the impact of the epidemic, this survey chooses the network survey as the main method and the on-site survey as the auxiliary method. The questionnaire was prepared by Questionnaire Star and distributed to the consumers of well-known digital electronic stores network mall with the help of network WeChat group and QQ group, who filled in the questionnaire online, and the questionnaire was collected simultaneously.

From September 25 to October 30, 2020, 737 questionnaires were collected, 7 invalid questionnaires were removed, and 731 valid questionnaires were collected. According to the suggestion of Hair et al. (2006), the sample size should be at least 5 times of the questions, and 10-20 times is the best. The questionnaire items in this study are 9 types with a total of

29 questions, and 731 valid questionnaires have been obtained. Therefore, the sample size of this study is appropriate.

Table 3.1 Distribution of survey sample sources

	Distributed	Collected	Effective	Total number of valid questionnaires
On site	327 copies	319 copies	313 copies	731 copies
Web-based approach			419 copies	

Findings

In this study, there are 4 demographic variables including gender, occupation, age and educational background. The statistical data analysis of the survey sample is shown in Table 4.1.

Table 4.1 Characteristic analysis of sample data

Name	Options	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gender	Female	342	46.79%
	Male	389	53.21%
Educational background	High School and below	167	22.85%
	Undergraduate or specialist degrees	431	58.96%
Age	Master and above	133	18.19%
	Under 25 years old	214	29.27%
	26-40 years old	157	21.48%
	41-55 years old	122	16.69%
Monthly salary level	Over 56 years old	238	32.56%
	6,000 and below	104	14.23%
	6,000 to 10,000	247	33.79%
	10,000 to 15,000	256	35.02%
	15,000 and above	124	16.96%
Total		731	100.00%

1. Gender: In terms of gender distribution, 389 respondents were male, accounting for 53.21%; There were 342 women, accounting for 46.79%. From the above statistics, we can see that the difference between men and women is not obvious in terms of consumption of smart wearable devices.

2. Educational background: In terms of educational background, 58.96% of the respondents have undergraduate or specialist degrees; 133, or 18.19%, have postgraduate degrees or above; 167 people have high school degree or below, accounting for 22.85%. From the above statistics, those with undergraduate or specialist degrees or above are the main consumer groups of smart wearable products.

3. Age: In terms of age distribution, 214 people are under 25 years old, accounting for 29.27%; There are 157 people aged 26-40, accounting for 21.48%. There are 122 people aged 31-55, accounting for 16.69%. There are 238 people over 56 years old, accounting for 32.56%. From the above statistics, people over 56 years old and people under 25 years old are the main consumer groups of smart wearable products.

4. Monthly wage level: in terms of income level, the proportion of consumers with monthly income below 6,000 yuan is 14.23%; Consumers with monthly income of 6,000 to 10,000 accounted for 33.79%. Consumers with monthly income of 10,000 to 15,000 accounted for 35.02%. Consumers with monthly income of 15,000 and above accounted for 16.96%. From

the above statistics, consumers with a monthly income of 6,000 to 15,000 are the main consumer groups of smart wearable products, and the proportion of consumers with a monthly income of less than 6,000 yuan is not high.

Objective 1: To explore the variance explanation degree of influencing factors to the original variable

In this study, factor analysis was conducted for nine survey items, including perceived ease of use, perceived usefulness, device hardware and software design, device service system, device training and promotion, consumer subjective norms, consumer perceived risk, consumer innovative traits, and consumer purchase intention, and according to the adoption criteria advocated by Kaiser (1958), common factors with extracted eigenvalues greater than 1 were retained, and the question items with absolute values of factor loadings greater than 0.5 were retained.

Dependent Variable D: Test and analysis of the results of the survey on consumer purchase and use Intention

1. Reliability analysis

The dependent variable consumer purchase intention to use has three question items, D11: I think it is valuable for me to buy smart wearable devices; D12: I think it is wise for me to buy smart wearable devices; D13: I think it is very helpful for my life to buy smart wearable devices. In order to investigate the quality of the survey results of the three questions, the reliability analysis of the survey results of these three questions is first carried out. The analysis results are as follows in Table 4.2.

Table 4.2 Reliability analysis of consumer purchase intention survey questions

Question item	Corrected Item-Total Correlation (CITC)	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted	Cronbach's alpha coefficient
D11	0.883	0.867	
D12	0.859	0.886	0.907
D13	0.811	0.904	

It can be seen from the above table that the reliability coefficient value is 0.960, which is greater than 0.9, indicating that the reliability of the research data is of high quality. Regarding the Cronbach's alpha if Item Deleted, after any item is deleted, the reliability coefficient will not increase significantly, so the item should not be deleted. Regarding the "CITC value", the CITC values of the analysis items are all greater than 0.4, indicating a good correlation between the analysis items and a good level of reliability. To sum up, the reliability coefficient value of the research data is higher than 0.9, which can be used for further analysis.

2. Analysis of validity

Validity research is used to analyze whether a measurement item is reasonable and meaningful, and validity analysis is conducted using factor analysis, a method of data analysis, to verify the level of validity of the data through a comprehensive analysis of KMO values, communalities, percentage of variance values, and factor loading coefficient values, respectively. The KMO value is used to determine the validity, the communalities value is used to exclude unreasonable research items, the percentage of variance value is used to indicate the level of information extraction, and the factor loading coefficient is used to measure the correspondence between factors (dimensions) and items. KMO and Bartlett's

Test were used to verify the validity of consumer purchase and use intentions. The analysis results are as follows in Table 4.3.

Table 4.3 Validity analysis results of consumer purchase and use intention survey questions

Name	Factor loading coefficient	Communality (common factor variance)
D11	0.950	0.903
D12	0.938	0.880
D13	0.913	0.834
Eigen value (Unrotated)	2.616	-
% of Variance (Unrotated)	87.205%	-
Cumulative % of Variance (Unrotated)	87.205%	-
Eigen value (Rotated)	2.616	-
% of Variance (Rotated)	87.205%	-
Cumulative % of Variance (Rotated)	87.205%	-
KMO value	0.748	-
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	192.124	-
df	3	-
p value	0.000	-

According to the results of the above variable reliability, validity and factor analysis, the factor loading coefficient, weight, average value, KMO value, P value, percentage of variance and Cronbach's alpha coefficient of all survey items can be obtained. According to the comprehensive analysis of these coefficients and data, it can be found that all of them passed the Bartlett's test of sphericity ($p < 0.05$), and the validity of the study data was good, which satisfied the prerequisite requirements of factor analysis. At the same time, the calculation of the question weights provided a method for calculating the specific data of the nine variables more accurately, and these preparations provided the data basis for the subsequent structured path analysis.

Objective 2 of the study: Difference analysis of demographic variables on survey items

Difference analysis of gender on survey items

To explore whether gender makes a difference in each survey item, gender was used as a grouping variable, and nine survey items, perceived ease of use (C1), perceived usefulness (C2), device hardware and software design (A1), education, training and promotion (A2), background support and service (A3), consumer, subjective norms (B1), consumer innovative characteristics (B2), consumer perceived risk (B3), and purchase intention (D) etc. as test variables for t-test, and their results are shown in Table 5.

In table 4.43:

- (1) The evaluation score of males and females in the survey item of perceived ease of use is 5.717 and 5.535, indicating that males are slightly better than females in terms of the ease of use of smart wearable devices, but on the whole, it does not reach a significant level.
- (2) The evaluation score of males and females in the survey item of perceived usefulness is 5.792 and 6.211. This shows that in terms of perceived usefulness, the overall average value of women is significantly higher than that of men, indicating that in terms of the usefulness of smart wearable devices, women are significantly stronger than men, with a P value of 0.033 reaching a significant level, indicating that in terms of perceived usefulness, women are significantly higher than men, and reach a significant level.
- (3) The evaluation score of males and females in the survey item of the device software and hardware design is 6.176 and 5.932. This shows that the overall average value of women is

slightly lower than that of men in terms of device software and hardware design, and that men are slightly stronger than women in terms of software and hardware design of smart wearable devices, but overall, does not not reached a significant level.

Table 4.4 Difference analysis of gender on survey items

Level Classification		Gender		T-value	P-value
		Male (N=159)	Female (N=167)		
Perceived ease of use (C1)		5.717	5.535	0.426	0.352
Perceived usefulness (C2)		5.792	6.211	0.986	0.033*
	Device software and hardware design (A1)	6.176	5.932	0.327	0.269
Product Level	Education, Training and Promotion (A2)	5.821	6.121	0.905	0.008*
	Background support and services (A3)	5.687	5.817	1.413	0.111
	Consumer subjective norms (B1)	5.014	5.518	0.822	0.000**
Consumer Level	Consumer Innovation Characteristics (B2)	5.904	5.517	0.322	0.000*
	Consumer perceived risk (B3)	5.039	5.217	1.226	0.115
Intention to buy (D)		4.924	5.115	1.903	0.102

* means p value is less than 0.05; ** means p value is less than 0.01

The research results show that (1) perceived ease of use, perceived usefulness, backend support and services, perceived risk, innovation traits and intention to use reflected significant differences in academic qualifications. (2) The difference analysis results of educational background on each survey items show that in terms of background support and services, consumer innovation characteristics and purchase intention, the survey evaluation scores of undergraduate and specialist degrees or above are significantly higher than those with educational background in high school or below. (3) The difference analysis results of the monthly income level on each survey items show that there are significant differences in the monthly income level on consumers' perceived usefulness, education, training and promotion, innovation characteristics and use intention. Among them, consumers with incomes of 10,000 to 15,000 and 15,000 or more have significantly higher perceived usefulness of smart wearable products, while consumers with monthly incomes of 6,000 or less have significantly lower perceived usefulness evaluation. This indicates that smart wearable products are technology-based products, and consumers generally have a higher level of income to purchase such products above a certain level. This provides a reference for the marketing design of intelligent wearable products in the later period. (4) The difference analysis results of age on each survey item show that there are significant differences in consumer perceived ease of use, perceived usefulness, device hardware and software design, education, training and promotion, background support and services, subjective norms,

perceived risk, innovative characteristics and intention to use all in terms of age. Among them, consumers 25 and below have a significantly higher perceived of ease of use of smart wearable products, followed by consumers 26-40 years old, and consumers over 56 years old have a significantly lower perceived of ease of use. In terms of perceived usefulness, consumers under 25 and consumers over 56 years old have higher evaluation scores, which is relatively consistent with the evaluation scores of consumers' shopping willingness. In terms of purchase intention, consumers under 25 years old have significantly higher purchase intention than other age levels, followed by the overall performance of consumers over 55 years old, and are also the main consumers of smart wearable products. In terms of education, training and promotion, consumers over 56 years old perform significantly higher than other age groups. In terms of consumer innovation characteristics, consumers in low-age groups are generally higher than consumers in high-age groups, which provides direction and data support for the planning of later industries.

Conclusion

1. The results of the empirical analysis of the explanatory degree of the variables by each question item of the factors influencing the purchase intention of smart wearable devices show that (1) The KMO value of the survey results of mediating variables perceived usefulness is 0.774, and the validity of the research data is good; the percentage of variance is 78.42%, and the percentage of variance is high, and the Cronbach's alpha coefficient is 0.847. (2) The KMO value of the survey results of mediating variables perceived usefulness is 0.687, and the validity of the research data is good; the percentage of variance is 77.86%, and the percentage of variance is higher, and the Cronbach's alpha coefficient is 0.830. (3) The KMO value of the survey results of the independent variable software and hardware design of device is 0.667, and the validity of the research data is good; the percentage of variance is 73.41%, the percentage of variance is higher, and the Cronbach's alpha coefficient is 0.798. (4) The KMO value of the survey results of the independent variable education, training and promotion is 0.636, and the validity of the research data is good; the percentage of variance is 65.06%, the percentage of variance is higher, and the Cronbach's alpha coefficient is 0.722. (5) The KMO value of the survey results of the independent variable background support and service is 0.634, and the validity of the research data is good; the percentage of variance is 70.436%, the percentage of variance is higher, and the Cronbach's alpha coefficient is 0.789. (6) The KMO value of the survey results of the independent variable consumer subjective norms is 0.714, and the validity of the research data is good; the percentage of variance is 74.780%, the percentage of variance is higher, and the Cronbach's alpha coefficient is 0.831. (7) The KMO value of the survey results of the independent variable consumer innovation characteristics is 0.709, and the validity of the research data is good; the percentage of variance is 74.111%, the percentage of variance is higher, and the Cronbach's alpha coefficient is 0.814. (8) The KMO value of the survey results of the independent variable consumer perceived risk is 0.675, and the validity of the research data is good; the percentage of variance is 66.625%, the percentage of variance is higher, and the Cronbach's alpha coefficient is 0.747. (9) The KMO value of the survey results of the independent variable consumer perceived risk is 0.748, and the validity of the research data is good; the percentage of variance is 87.20%, the percentage of variance is higher, and the Cronbach's alpha coefficient is 0.907. From the results of the above analysis, it can be seen that the survey results have a high degree of credibility and the overall effect of the data is good, which is consistent with the moderation of factor analysis to further explore its internal relationships.

According to relevant theories and literature analysis, screen out various influencing variables that affect consumers' purchase of smart wearable devices, construct an analysis scale of various variables, and explore the explanatory ability of various factors of smart

wearable device purchase intention to the original variables through investigation and analysis. The analysis results show that the explanatory degree of survey questions to each variable is generally more than 65%, and the survey scale constructed in this paper has a high explanatory degree to each influencing variable of consumers' purchase intention.

References

- Abbas, H. A. and Hamdy, H. I. (2015). Determinants of continuance intention factor in Kuwait communication market: Case study of Zain-Kuwait. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 49(0), 648-657.
- Adnan Abd. H, Fahmi, Z. A. R., Azlina, A. B. and Abdullah, W. S. W. (2015). The effects of perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use on continuance intention to use e-government. *Procedia Economics and Finance*, 35, 644 – 649.
- Ajzen, I. (1985). From intentions to actions: A theory of planned behavior. In action-control: From cognition to behavior; Kuhl, J., Beckman, J., Eds.; *Springer Science & Business Media: Berlin, Germany*, 11-39.
- Ajzen, I. (1991). The theory of planned behavior. *Organizational behavior and Human Decision Processes*, 50(2), 179-211.
- Akturan, U. and Tezcan, N. (2012). Mobile banking adoption of the youth market: perceptions and intentions. *Marketing Intelligence & Planning*, 30(4), 444-459.
- Aldas-Manzano, J., Lassala-Navarre, C., Ruiz-Mafe, C. and Sanz-Blas, S. (2009). The role of consumer innovativeness and perceived risk in online banking usage. *International Journal of Bank Marketing*, 27(1), 53-75.
- Ali, A. (2018). Drivers and barriers of mobile commerce: The role of consumers' personal innovativeness. *Goodman School of Business, Brock University, St. Catharines-Ontario*.
- Ali, M. E., Wong, K. W. and Fung C. C. (2016). Perceived ease of use and perceived usefulness of social media for e-learning in Libyan higher education: A structural equation modeling analysis. *International Journal of Information and Education Technology*, 6(3).
- Amin, Md. K., Afrin, A., Afrina, A. and Afia, A. (2015). Applying the technology acceptance model in examining Bangladeshi consumers' behavioral intention to use mobile wallet: *PLS-SEM approach*. Retrieved December 21-23, 2015, from 10.1109/ICCITechn.2015.7488049
- Anderson, J., and Gerbing, D. W. (1988). Structural equation modeling in practice: A review and recommended two-step approach. *Psychological Bulletin*, 103(3), 411-423.
- Aroean, L., and Michaelidou, N. (2014). A taxonomy of mobile phone consumers: insights for marketing managers. *Journal of Strategic Marketing*, 22(1), 73-89.
- Arslan, Y., Gecti, F., Hayrettin, Z. (2013). Examining perceived risk and its influence on attitudes: A study on private label consumers in turkey. *Journal of Asian Social Science*, 9(4), 158-156.
- Aygun T., Ayseguul, O. T. and Cemal, Z. (2015). A theoretical model proposal: personal innovativeness and user involvement as antecedents of unified theory of acceptance and use of technology. Retrieved, from <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2015.11.327>
- Bagozzi, R. P. and Yi, Y. (1988). On the evaluation of structural equation models. *Academic of Marketing Science*, 16 (1), 76-94.
- Bagozzi, R.P., Yi, Y. and Phillips, L.W. (1991). Assessing construct validity in organizational research. *Administrative Science Quarterly*, 36, 421-458.
- Baker-Eveleth, L. and Stone, R. W. (2015). Usability, expectation, confirmation, and continuance intentions to use electronic textbooks. *Behaviour & Information Technology*, 1-13.
- Bargatzky, T. (1989). Innovation and the integration of social cultural systems. In S.E.van der Leeuw & R. Torrence (Ed.), *What's New?* 16-32.
- Bauer, R. A. (1960). Consumer behavior as risk taking. In Cox, D. (Ed.), *Risk taking and information handling in consumer behaviour*, 389-398. *Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press*.
- Bhatiasevi, V., and Yoopetch, C. (2015). The determinants of intention to use electronic booking among young users in Thailand. *Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Management*, 23, 1-11.
- Bian P.. (2012). A Review of Research on Technology Acceptance Models. *Library Studies*, (01), 2-6+10. doi:10.15941/j.cnki.issn1001-0424.2012.01.022.

- Black, N. J., Lockett, A., Winklhofer, H. and Ennew, C. (2001). The adoption of Internet financial services: a qualitative study. *International Journal of Retail & Distribution Management*, 29(8), 390-398.
- Bresciani, Sabrina and Eppler, Martin J. (2015). Extending TAM to information visualization: A framework for evaluation. *Electronic Journal of Information System Evaluation*, 18 (1). 46-58.
- Brown, J. D. (1996). Testing in language programs. Upper Saddle River, NJ: Prentice Hall Regents. Retrieved Autumn, 2000, from http://hosted.jalt.org/test/bro_8.htm
- Chai, S.H. & Zhang Y.N.. (2019). A study on the factors influencing consumers' overseas proxy shopping on cross-border e-commerce platforms based on TAM. *Journal of Qingdao University of Science and Technology (Social Science Edition)*, (02), 17-23. doi:10.16800/j.cnki.jqstss.2019.02.022.
- Chen Y.. (2018). Analysis of Exhibition App Acceptance and Antecedents Based on Technology Acceptance Model Theory. *Business and Economic Research*, (05), 183-186.
- Chen, C.H. & Li, X.Y.. (2018). A study on the factors influencing citizens' willingness to use shared bicycles. *Journal of Management*, (11), 1601-1610.
- Chen, D.H., Xi, L.B., Tang, S.L. & Lu, F.. (2009). Research on mobile Internet marketing strategy based on technology acceptance model. *Mobile Communication*, (10), 78-82.
- Chen, J.V., Yen, D.C. and Chen, K. (2009). The acceptance and diffusion of the innovative smart phone use: a case study of a delivery service company in logistics. *Information and Management*, 46(4), 241-248.
- Chen, Jin.. (2019). Analysis of factors influencing online reviews on consumers' purchase intention in the context of "Internet+". *Modern Marketing (Business Edition)*, (06), 96-97.
- Chen, K. & Zhao, N.. (2018). A study on the mechanism of long-term care insurance purchase intention: influencing factors, modes of action and pathways. *Financial Theory and Practice*, (06), 99-103.
- Chen, L. & Yang, X. G.. (2015). A study of factors influencing consumers' willingness to choose O2O model consumption: Based on (TAM) technology acceptance model. *Management Observation*, (28), 51-56.
- Chen, L.M., Chen, H.Y. & Yang, Z.J.. (2017). Research on the adoption intention of rural mobile information service users based on technology acceptance model. *Electronic Commerce*, (10), 57-59. doi:10.14011/j.cnki.dzsw.2017.10.024.
- Chen, Q.. (2019). Global smart wearable device development characteristics and trends. *Shanghai Informatization*, (04), 78-80.
- Cheng, H. & Le, Q. (2018). A study on the willingness to use social financial products based on technology acceptance model: the example of "WeChat Wallet". *Research in Financial Economics*, (01), 117-128.
- Chin, W. W., and Newsted, P. R. (1999). Structural equation modeling analysis with small samples using partial least squares. In R. Hoyle (Ed.). *Statistical strategies for small samples research*, 307-341.
- Chiu Y. B., Lin C.P. and Tang L. L. (2005). Gender differs: assessing a model of online purchase intentions in e-tail service. *Int. J. service Industry Manag*, 16 (5).
- Choudhury, V. and Karahanna, E. (2008). The relative advantage of electronic channels: A multidimensional view. *Mis Quarterly*, 32(1).
- communities. *Journal Behaviour & Information Technology*, 29(6), 557-570.
- Cowart, K. O., Fox, G. L. and Wilson, A. E. (2008). A structural look at consumer innovativeness and self-congruence in new product purchases. *Psychology & Marketing*, 25(12), 1111-1130.
- Cronbach, L. (1951). Coefficient alpha and the internal structure of tests. *Psychometrika*, 16(3), 297-337.
- Cronbach, L. J. and Meehl, P. C. (1955). Construct validity in psychological tests. *Psychological Bulletin*, 52, 281-302.
- Cuieford, J. P. (1965). *Fundamental Statistics in Psychology and Education*. N.Y: McGraw-Hill.
- Dai Y.L., Gu D.X., Lu W.X. & Liang C.Y.. (2016). A study on hospital information system continuous use intention - based on technology acceptance model and expectation confirmation theory. *Computer Science*, (07), 240-244.
- Dai, B. & Liu, Y.Z.. (2012). A study of SNS usage intention based on technology acceptance model and perceived popularity. *Science and Technology Progress and Countermeasures*, (24), 47-51.

- Davis, F. D. (1986). A technology acceptance model for empirically testing new end-user information system : theory and results. *MIT Sloan School of management, Cambridge-MA*.
- Davis, Fred D., Bagozzi, Richard P. and Warshaw, Paul R. (1989) .User acceptance of computer technology: a comparison of two theoretical models. *Management Science*, 35(8), 982-1003.
- Davis,F.D (1986) .A technology acceptance model for empirically testing new end- user information systems:theory and results.Ph.D.dissertation, *MIT Sloan School of Management,Cambridge,MA*.
- Davis,F.D (1989) .Perceived usefulness,perceived ease of use,and user acceptance of information technology. *MIS Quarterly*. (13):319- 340.
- Davis,F.D (1993) .User Acceptance of Information Technology:System Characteristics,User Perceptions and Behavioral Impacts. *International Journal of Man- Machine Studies*,38(3):475-487.
- Davis,F.D.,Bagozzi,R.P.&Warshaw,P.R (1989) .User acceptance of computer technology: A comparison of two theoretical models. *Management Science*, (35):982- 1003.
- Deng, S., Liu, J. & Yang, H.M.. (2020). Research on government data openness based on user acceptance model. *Secretary*, (03),27-38.
- Dong, X.W. & Gu, J.Q.. (2020). A study on the factors influencing the willingness to use digital interactive teaching materials in colleges and universities based on TAM. *Design*, (13),130-132.
- Dong, X.W. & Qin, Z.T.. (2019). Research on the interface design of trade union mobile service APP based on user behavior model - taking Zhejiang trade union APP as an example. *Industrial Design*, (11),72-73.
- Dong, X.W., Ye, Z.J., Xu, N.N., Wang, Y.L., Guan, J.J. & Chen, J.. (2020). A study on tourists' usage intention online tour guides based on TAM and TRI. *Journal of Tourism*, (07), 24-35. doi:10.19765/j.cnki.1002-5006.2020.07.007.
- Du, H.Y., Zhang, X.R. & Yuan, R.X.. (2019). Tri-network convergence business adoption attitude model based on SCT and TAM. *Journal of Beijing University of Information Science and Technology (Natural Science Edition)*, (06), 47-52. doi:10.16508/j.cnki.11-5866/n.2019.06.009.
- Du, J.L., Gao L.Q., Liu, Y., Li Bin & Yang Z.M.. (2019). A study on the factors influencing the purchase intention of new energy vehicle consumers in Beijing, Tianjin and Hebei. *Value Engineering*, (19), 220-223. doi:10.14018/j.cnki.cn13-1085/n.2019.19.073.
- Du, Q.Y.. (2018). Research on the acceptance and usage behavior of Zhihu users based on TAM model. *Journal of Guangzhou University (Social Science Edition)*, (06), 38-43.
- Dun, S., Chen, Q., Xie, Z.M. & Hu, S.P.. (2013). A study of the mechanism of perceived product innovativeness on purchase intention - Evidence from the smartphone industry. *Systems Engineering*.
- Echchabi, A. and Abd. Aziz, H. (2012). Empirical investigation of customers' perception and adoption towards Islamic banking services in Morocco. *Middle-East Journal of Scientific Research*, 12 (6), 849-858.
- Eunil, P. and Sang, J. K. (2016). The adoption of teaching assistant robots: a technology acceptance model approach, *Program*, 50(4), 354-366.
- Fagan, M.H., Neill, S. and Wooldridge, B. R. (2008). Exploring the intention to use computers: An empirical investigation of the role of intrinsic motivation, extrinsic motivation and perceived ease of use. *Journal of Computer Information Systems*, 48(3).
- Falk, M. C., Chassy, B. M., Harlander, S. K., Hoban, T. J., McGloughlin M. N. and Akhlaghi, A. R. (2002). Food biotechnology: Benefits and concerns. *Journal of Nutrition*, 32, 1384–1390.
- Fang, X.H.. (2019). Research on factors influencing the purchase intention of new energy vehicle consumers and guiding policies. *Modern Trade Industry*, (21), 168-169. doi:10.19311/j.cnki.1672-3198.2019.21.085.
- Farzianpour, F., Pishdar, M., Shakib, M.D. and Toloun, M.R.S. (2014). Consumers' perceived risk and its effect on adoption of online banking services. *American Journal of Applied Sciences*, 11(1), 47-56.
- Featherman, M. S. and Pavlou, P. A. (2003). Predicting e-services adoption: a perceived risk facets perspective. *International Journal of Human-Computer Studies*, 59(4), p.457.
- Fishbein, M. & Ajzen, Icek (1975) . Belief, attitude, intention and behaviour: An introduction to theory and research. *Reading,MA:Addison-Wesley*.

- Flora A. Kimathi & Zhang, Y. (2019). Exploring the General Extended Technology Acceptance Model for e-Learning Approach on Student's Usage intention on e-Learning System in University of Dar es Salaam. *Creative Education*, (1).
- Fred D. Davis (1985). A technology acceptance model for empirically testing new end-user information systems. *Sloan School of Management, US-Cambridge*.
- Frewer, L. J., Howard, C. and Shepherd, R. (1997). Public concern in the United Kingdom about general and specific applications of genetic engineering: Risk, benefits and ethics. *Science, Technology and Human Values*, 22, 98-124.
- Gao F.R. (2010). New advances in the study of information technology acceptance models. *Journal of Intelligence*, (06), 170-176.
- Gao Q. & Yu W.H. (2018). Current status of smart wearable devices in elderly patients with dementia. *Journal of Nursing*, (14), 33-36. doi:10.16460/j.issn1008-9969.2018.14.033.
- Gao, T., Rohm, A. J., Sultan, F. and Huang, S. (2012). Antecedents of consumer attitudes toward mobile marketing: A comparative study of youth markets in the United States and China. *Thunderbird International Business Review*, 54(2), 211-224.
- Gefen, D., Straub, D. and Boudreau, M.C. (2000). Structural equation modelling and regression: Guidelines for research practice. *Communications of the Association for Information Systems*, 4(7), 2000, 1-78.
- George, D. and Mallery, P. (2003). SPSS for Windows step by step: A simple guide and reference. 11.0 update (4th ed.). *Boston: Allyn & Bacon*.
- Guo, Y. Z. & Li, S. M. (2018). An empirical study of consumers' willingness to use mobile payment to purchase tourism products - based on technology acceptance model and theory of planned behavior model. *Journal of Sichuan University, (Philosophy and Social Science Edition)*, (06), 159-170.
- Hair, J. F., Sarstedt, M., Hopkins, L. and Kuppelwieser, V. G. (2014). Partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM): An emerging tool in business research. *European Business Review*, 26(2), 106-121.
- Hair, J. F., Sarstedt, M., Ringle and Mena, J. A. (2012). An assessment of the use of partial least squares structural equation modeling in marketing research. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 40, 414-433.
- Han X. (2017). Integrating a meta-analysis of technology acceptance models: Based on 10 years of domestic research literature. *Journal of Intelligence*, (08), 150-155+174.
- Han, J.F. & Tan, D.J. (2013). A review of digital library acceptance research based on technology acceptance model. *Digital Library Forum*, (03), 32-38.
- Han, Z.S., Gao, N.N. & Cao, Z.B. (2019). An empirical study of higher vocational students' mobile learning behavior based on TAM3--Taking Blue Ink Cloud Classroom Education Software as an example. *China Educational Technology Equipment*, (08), 18-20+23.
- He J.H., Mo Z., Liu H.W. & Ai D.X. (2013). A study on mobile marketing acceptance model based on technology influence. *Statistics and Decision Making*, (22), 171-173. doi:10.13546/j.cnki.tjyc.2013.22.047.
- He, J.P. & Huang, X.S. (2020). Smartphone use and achieving well-being among urban older adults: based on intergenerational support theory and technology acceptance model. *International Journalism*, (03), 49-73. doi:10.13495/j.cnki.cjjc.20200409.003.
- He, J.R. & Wu, S.Y. (2018). Empirical Research on the Influencing Factors of WeChat User Acceptance and Use Behavior in University Library. *Library Research*, (05), 115-121.
- Henseler, J. (2012). PLS-MGA: A non-parametric approach to partial least squares-based multi-group analysis. In: Gaul, W.A., Geyer-Schulz, A., Schmidt-Thieme, L., and Kunze, J. (eds.), *Challenges at the interface of data analysis, computer science, and optimization. Studies in Classification, Data Analysis, and Knowledge Organization*, 495- 501.
- Henseler, J., Hubona, G. and Ray, P.A. (2016). Using PLS path modeling in new technology research: updated guidelines. *Industrial Management and Data Systems*, 116 (1), 2-20.
- Henseler, J., Ringle, C. M., and Sinkovics, R. R. (2009). The use of partial least squares path modeling in international marketing, *Advances in International Marketing*, 20, 277-320.

- Hirunyawipada, T. and Paswan, A.K. (2006). Consumer innovativeness and perceived risk: implications for high technology product adoption. *Journal of Consumer Marketing*, 23(4), 182-98.
- Ho, C. H., and Wu, W. (2011). Role of innovativeness of consumer in relationship between perceived attributes of new products and intention to adopt. *International Journal of Electronic Business Management*, 9(3).
- Hou, P. & Zhou, M.R.. (2018). Analysis of the factors influencing college students' acceptance of WeChat marketing based on TAM model - taking Nanjing University of Posts and Telecommunications as an example. *Business and Management*, (05), 131-137. doi:10.16517/j.cnki.cn12-1034/f.2018.05.038.
- Hu, A.A., Jiang, J. & Huang, L.H.. (2007). A study of ERP system implementation model based on IT user acceptance theory. *Science and Technology Management*, (08), 20-26.
- Hu, L.J., Tang, Y. & Mao, Y.. (2015). Factors influencing the use of small pure electric vehicles based on technology acceptance model. *Science and Technology Management Research*, (05), 122-125+130.
- Hu, Q.L. & Sun, Q.. (2008). An analysis of consumers' willingness to use mobile payment using an integrated technology acceptance model. *Statistics and Decision Making*, (06), 119-121.
- Huang, S. H., Xiao, J. C. & Jin, Y. N.. (2020). A study on factors influencing consumers' continuous purchase intention on social e-commerce platforms based on S-O-R theory. *Soft Science*, (06), 115-121. doi:10.13956/j.ss.1001-8409.2020.06.18.
- Igbaria, M., T. Guimaraes and G. B. Davis. (1995). Testing the determinants of microcomputer usage Via a structural equation model. *Journal of Management Information Systems*, 11(4), 87-114.
- Imran, A. (2018). Personality traits, individual innovativeness and satisfaction with life. *Journal of Innovation & Knowledge*, 4 (2019), 38-4.
- Jacoby, J. and Kaplan, L.B. (1972). The components of perceived risk. In: Venkatesan, M., editor. *Advances in Consumer Research*. (3), Chicago, IL: *Association for Consumer Research*, 382-393.
- Jame Bryan L. Batara, Joanna Paula R. Mariblanca, Karlo Mar D. Kinaadman and Jandall Airon B. Go. (2018). The effect of consumer innovativeness, perceived benefits, perceived risk, and brand image in the decision to buy online, *University of San Carlos, Cebu-Philippines*.
- Janet, D. G. (1990). A review of the literature pertaining to 'perceived' risk and 'acceptable' risk and the methods used to estimate them. *Information Paper No. 14, Centre for Resource Management, University of Canterbury and Lincoln University*.
- Jayasingh, S., and Eze, U. (2009). An empirical analysis of consumer repurchase intention toward mobile coupons in Malaysia. *International Journal of Business and Information*, 4(2), 221-242.
- Jeffrey, B. C. (2009). The influence of perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, and subjective norm on the use of computed radiography systems: A pilot study, *The Ohio State University, United Stated-Columbus*.
- Jia, N. & Li, E. D.. (2019). Construction of a personalized health supervision platform based on smart wearable devices. *Computer Science*, (S1), 566-570.
- Jiang, L.. (2020). A study on the motivation of consumer online reviews based on SET and TAM. *Journal of University of Science and Technology Beijing (Social Science Edition)*, (01), 87-94.
- Jiao, Y.B.. (2007). A study of antecedents of customers' use of online banking - A view based on technology acceptance model. *Journal of Shanxi University of Finance and Economics*, (06), 94-100.
- Jin, Y. and Liu, Y.L. (2020). Research on users' willingness to use self-service book bars in urban neighborhoods--a survey based on Chongqing urban area. *New Century Library*, (08), 43-50. doi:10.16810/j.cnki.1672-514X.2020.08.007.
- Johnny, C. and Jonathan, W. (2018). A conceptual framework for the acceptance of drones. *The International Technology Management*, 7(1), 34-46.
- Joo, J. and Sang, Y. (2013). Exploring Koreans' smartphone usage: An integrated model of the technology acceptance model and uses and gratifications theory. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 29(6):2512-2518.
- Josephine, K., Peter, W. and Daniel, O. (2014). Determinants of acceptance and use of DHIS2: Survey instrument validation and preliminary findings using PLS-SEM. *Journal of Emerging Trends in Computing and Information Sciences*, 5, (8).

- Juliet, B. (2010). Perceived Usefulness, Perceived ease of use, attitude and usage of a new financial management system: a case study of Uganda national examinations board, *Makerere University Business School, Uganda-Kampala*.
- June, L. (2014). Are personal innovativeness and social influence critical to continue with mobile commerce?. *Internet Research*, 24(2), 134 – 159.
- June, L., Yu, C. S., Liu, C., James, Y. E. (2003). Technology acceptance model for wireless Internet. *Internet Research*, 13(3), 206-222.
- Khan, A. and Chavan, C.R. (2015). Factors affecting on-line shopper's behavior for electronic goods purchasing in Mumbai: An empirical study. *International Journal in Management and Social Science*, 3(3), 467-476.
- Kieran, M. (1991). Predicting user intentions: Comparing the technology acceptance model with the theory of planned behavior. *Information Systems Research*, 2(3), 173-191.
- Kim, C., Mirusmonov, M. and Lee, I. (2010). An empirical examination of factors influencing the intention to use mobile payment. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 26(3), 310-322.
- Kim, J. (2016). An extended technology acceptance model in behavioral intention toward hotel tablet apps with moderating effects of gender and age. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 28(8), 1535-1553.
- Kim, J. and Lennon, S. J. (2013). Effects of reputation and website quality on online consumers' emotion, perceived risk and purchase intention: Based on the stimulus-organism-response model. *Journal of Research in Interactive Marketing*, 7(1), 33-56.
- Kim, Y. and Lee, H. S. (2014). Quality, perceived usefulness, user satisfaction, and intention to use: An empirical study of ubiquitous personal robot service. *Asian Social Science*, 10(11), 1911-2025.
- Kiran J. Patel and Hiren J. Patel. (2018). Adoption of internet banking services in Gujarat: An extension of TAM with perceived security and social influence. *International Journal of Bank Marketing*, 36(1), 147-169.
- Kolodinsky, J. M., Hogarth, J. M. and Hilgert, M. A. (2004). The adoption of electronic banking technologies by US consumers. *International Journal of Bank Marketing*, 22(4), 238-259.
- Kuang, W. B. & Jia, Y. D.. (2018). A study of news client user behavior and habits based on technology acceptance model. *Journal of Shenzhen University (Humanities and Social Sciences Edition)*, (01), 95-102.
- Kwon, S. J., Park, E. and Kim, K. J. (2014). What drives successful social networking services? A comparative analysis of user acceptance of Facebook and Twitter. *The social Science Journal*.
- Lam, S. Y., Chiang, J. and Parasuraman, A. (2008). The effects of the dimensions of technology readiness on technology acceptance: An empirical analysis. *Journal of Interactive Marketing*, 22(4), 19-39.
- Lee, D.Y. and M.R. Lehto. (2013). User acceptance of YouTube for procedural learning: An extension of the technology acceptance model. *Comput. Educ.*, 61, 193-208.
- Lee, M. C. (2009). Factors influencing the adoption of internet banking: An integration of TAM and TPB with perceived risk and perceived benefit. *Electronic Commerce Research and Applications*, 8(3), 130-141.
- Lee, S. and Kim, B. G. (2009). Factors affecting the usage of intranet: A confirmatory study. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 25(1), 191-201.
- Lee, Y. H., Hsieh, Y. C. and Hsu, C. N. (2011). Adding innovation diffusion theory to the technology acceptance model: Supporting employees' intentions to use E-learning systems. *Educational Technology & Society*, 14(4), 124-137.
- Leeuw, S. E. van der and Torrence, R. (1989). Introduction: What's new about innovation? In S.E. van der Leeuw & R. Torrence (Eds.), *What's new? (1-15)*. Boston: UNWIN HYMAN.
- Lei, J. & Li, X.. (2014). A study on the reliability and validity of mobile payment usage intention based on extended technology acceptance model. *Statistics and Decision Making*, (18), 98-100. doi:10.13546/j.cnki.tjyc.2014.18.019.
- Lemuria, C. and Ronald, C. (2011). The impact of trust and relative advantage on internet voting diffusion. *Journal of Theoretical and Applied Electronic Commerce Research*, 6(3), 28-42.
- Li Q.H., Jiang Y.Y., Zhong Y. & Zeng G.. (2017). A study of user technology acceptance model for mobile medical applications. *China Market*, (33), 141-143. doi:10.13939/j.cnki.zgsc.2017.33.141.

- Li, H. and Liu, Y. (2014). Understanding post-adoption behaviors of e-service users in the context of online travel services. *Information & Management*, 51(8),1043-1052.
- Li, H. Q., Wu, C. & Fan, C. M.. (2018). Research on the influencing factors of residents' green travel under intelligent transportation technology - Root analysis based on TPB and TAM integrated model. *Modern Urban Research*, (12), 2-8.
- Li, J. & Han, X.. (2019). Citizen voluntariness, technology acceptance and online participation:An empirical study based on structural equation modeling. *Journal of Intelligence*, (02), 201-207.
- Li, J.X., Gong, M.G. & Gao Z.J.. (2015). A visual analysis of theoretical research on technology acceptance models. *Modern Intelligence*, (12), 99-105.
- Li, W., Huang, Y. & Yang, F.. (2018). A study on college students' willingness to adopt mobile news client and its influencing factors: from the perspective of technology acceptance model and innovation diffusion theory. *Books & Intelligence*, (04), 62-71.
- Li, Y.X. & Pan, J.P. (2019). A study on the factors influencing the development of bicycle sharing industry based on TAM and factor analysis. *Logistics Engineering and Management*, (11), 122-125.
- Li, Z & Zhu, T. (2017). A study on TAM-based social software users' usage intention consistently. *Computer Knowledge and Technology*, (22), 43-46. doi:10.14004/j.cnki.ckt.2017.2492.
- Lin, A. and Chen, N. C. (2012). Cloud computing as an innovation: Percepation, attitude, and adoption. *International Journal of Information Management*, 32(6), 533-540.
- Lin, C. Y., Chao, Y. C. and Tang, T. W. (2017). Why not be "smarter"? Examining the factors that influence the behavioral intentions of non-smartphone users. *Industrial Management & Data Systems*, 117(1), 32-49.
- Lin, W. S. and Wang, C. H. (2012). Antecedences to continued intentions of adopting e-learning system in blended learning instruction: A contingency framework based on models of information system success and task-technology fit. *Computers & Education*, 58(1), 88-99.
- Littler, D. and Melanthiou, D. (2006). Consumer perceptions of risk and uncertainty and the implications for behaviour towards innovative retail services: the case of internet banking. *Journal of retailing and consumer services*, 13(6), 431-443.
- Liu, G. & Yang, J.Q.. (2019). An empirical study of e-payment user adoption behavior based on TAM and IDT models. *Technology and Management*, (03), 63-70. doi:10.16315/j.stm.2019.03.015.
- Liu, H.Y. & Yan, M.J. (2019). A survey and analysis of usage intention smart teaching tools based on integrated technology acceptance model. *Higher Education Forum*, (12), 54-59.
- Liu, M. J.. (2016). Research on improving the effectiveness of taxation WeChat platform based on technology acceptance model - taking Guangxi State Tax 12366 as an example. *Economic Research Reference*, (35), 43-48. doi:10.16110/j.cnki.issn2095-3151.2016.35.011.
- Liu, M.Z. & Qiu, Z.H.. (2020). Reader Needs and Market Satisfaction: Research and Application of Reading App Evaluation System. *Library Science Research*, (08), 73-84. doi:10.15941/j.cnki.issn1001-0424.2020.08.011.
- Liu, X. D., Lv, X. Y. & Ren, P. R.. (2017). Research on user adoption behavior of sports and fitness app--PESE behavior model. *Enterprise Economics*, (11), 48-54. doi:10.13529/j.cnki.enterprise.economy.2017.11.007.
- Liu, X.J., Liu, L. & Fu, H.L.. (2020). A study of factors influencing urban residents' recycled water reuse behavior based on TAM and perceived risk. *Ecological Economics*, (06), 102-106.
- Liu, Y. C. and Huang, Y. M. (2015). Using the UTAUT model to examine the acceptance behavior of synchronous collaboration to support peer translation. *The Jaltcall Journal*, 11(1), 77-91.
- Long, Y.T., Zhao, Y.T., Zhang, L. & Liu, R.. (2020). Analysis of factors influencing the purchase intention of new energy vehicle consumers--Based on a market survey in Beijing. *China Business Journal*, (04), 3-4. doi:10.19699/j.cnki.issn2096-0298.2020.04.003.
- Lu, H.W. & Yang, P.B. (2017). A study of O2O high-frequency consumption usage intention in mobile internet. *Research in Business Economics*, (15), 40-42.
- Lu, J., Yao, J. and Yu, C. (2005). Personal innovativeness, social influences, and adoption of wireless internet services via mobile technology. *Strategic Information Systems*, 14(3), 245-268.
- Lu, Y.B. & Xu, H.M.. (2006). A review of empirical studies on technology acceptance models. *Research and Development Management*, (03), 93-99.
- Luarn, P. and Lin, H. H. (2005). Toward an understanding of the behavioral intention to use mobile banking. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 21(6), 873-891.

- Luo, X., Li, H., Zhang, J. and Shim, J. P. (2010). Examining multi-dimensional trust and multi-faceted risk in initial acceptance of emerging technologies: An empirical study of mobile banking services. *Decision Support Systems*, 49(2), 222-234.
- Luo, Y.K.. (2020). Analysis of factors influencing consumers' online purchase intention based on personalized recommendation. *Research in Business Economics*, (09), 75-79.
- Ma Q, Qin Y.T. & Yang L.H.. (2019). Research on the factors influencing the purchase intention of new energy vehicles and its policy incentive path. *Fudan Public Administration Review*, (02), 36-63.
- Maria, S. (2003). Consumer adoption of technological innovations. *European Journal of Innovation Management*, 6(2), 90-100.
- Massoud, M., Pham, V. K., Wong, W. K. and Ismail, B. (2018). E-purchase intention of Taiwanese consumers: *Sustainable mediation of perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use*. *Sustainability*, 10(1), 1-17.
- Meng, X. R., Deng, Z. H. & Wu, T. L.. (2020). A study on the factors influencing the intention of middle-aged and elderly users to use smart wearable devices. *Health Soft Science*, (08), 41-46.
- Ming J.R., Guo C.Q & Wang X.X. (2018). An empirical study of mobile library users' willingness to use based on UTAUT. *Library Studies*, (22), 81-90. doi:10.15941/j.cnki.issn1001-0424.2018.22.013.
- Ming, J.R. & Guo, C.Q.. (2018). A dynamic empirical study of mobile library users' willingness to use behaviors. *Library Construction*, (10), 73-79.
- Ming, J.R., Yu, S.Y., Yang, Y.N. & Huang, C.H.. (2014). Construction of a technology acceptance model for mobile libraries. *Intelligence Data Work*, (05), 49-55.
- Mirjana, P. B., Amer, C. and Jovana, Z. (2016). Technology acceptance model for business intelligence systems: Preliminary research. *Procedia Computer Science*, 100, 995-1001
- Mirza, H. H., Mohsen, D., Hamed, D. and Mojtaba, D. (2016). Factors affecting consume resistance to innovation in mobile phone industry. *International Journal of Asian Social Science*, 6(9), 497-509.
- Mitchell, V. W. (1999). Consumer perceived risk: conceptualization and models. *European Journal of marketing*, 33(1/2), 163-195.
- Mohamed, S. C. and Nizar, S. (2010). Rethinking the TAM model: time to consider fun. *Journal of Consumer Marketing*, 27(4), 336-344.
- Moon , J. and Kim, Y. (2001). Extending the TAM for a world-wide-web context. *Information and Management*, 38(4), 217-230.
- Moore, G.C. and Benbasat, I. (1991). Development of an instrument to measure the perceptions of adopting an information technology innovation. *Information Systems Research*, 2, 173-191.
- Morosan, C. and DeFranco, A. (2014). When tradition meets the new technology: An examination of the antecedents of attitudes and intentions to use mobile devices in private clubs. *International Journal of Hospitality Management*, 42, 126-136.
- Mou, J., Shin, D.-H. and Cohen, J. (2016). Understanding trust and perceived usefulness in the consumer acceptance of an e-service: A longitudinal investigation. *Behaviour & Information Technology*, 36(2), 125-139.
- Ni, J.F.. (2019). A study on the factors influencing the willingness to adopt BIM technology based on TAM. *Engineering Economics*, (12), 47-50. doi:10.19298/j.cnki.1672-2442.201912047.
- Nie J.. (2018). The influence of shopping motivation on consumers' acceptance and use of mobile shopping. *Journal of Wuzhou College*, (02), 17-24.
- Noh, M., Lee, K., Kim, S. and Garrison, G. (2013). Effects of collectivism on actual s-commerce use and the moderating effect of price consciousness. *Journal of Electronic Commerce Research*, 14(3), 244-260.
- Nunnally, J. C. (1978) *Psychometric Theory*. New York: Mcgraw-Hill.
- O' Cass, A. and Fenech, T. (2003). Web retailing adoption: Exploring the nature of internet users web retailing behavior. *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 10, 81- 94.
- Odabasi, Y. and Baris, G. (2002). *Tuketici Davranisi*, (3. Edition), Istanbul, MediaCat Kitaplari.
- Oded, N. and Chen, Y. (2008). Users' personality and perceived ease of use of digital libraries: The case for resistance to change. *Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology (JASIST)*, 59(5), 845-851.
- Ozbek, V., Gunalan, M., Koc, F., Sahin, N. K. and Kas, E. (2015). The effects of perceived risk and cost on technology acceptance: A study on tourists' use of online booking. *Journal of Social Sciences*, 13(2).

- Parisot, A. H. (1997). Distance education as a catalyst for changing teaching in the community college: Implications for institutional policy. *New Directions for Community Colleges*, 99, 5-13.
- Park, N., Kim, Y. C., Shon, H. Y. and Shim, H. (2013). Factors influencing smartphone use and dependency in South Korea. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 29(4), 1763-1770.
- Park, N., Mohja, R., Hou, J. H. and Lee, K. M. (2014). Understanding the acceptance of teleconferencing systems among employees: An extension of the technology acceptance model. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 39(0), 118-127.
- Park, Y. and Chen, J.V. (2007). Acceptance and adoption of the innovative use of smartphone. *Industrial Management and Data Systems*, 107(9), 1349-1365.
- Paul, P. (2001). Consumer intentions to adopt electronic commerce - incorporating trust and risk in the technology acceptance model. *Journal International Journal of Electronic Commerce*, 7(3), 101-134.
- Puschel, J., Afonso Mazzon, J., Mauro, C. and Hernandez, J. (2010). Mobile banking: Proposition of an integrated adoption intention framework. *International Journal of Bank Marketing*, 28, 389-409.
- R.A. Fisher. (1921). On the "probable error" of a coefficient of correlation deduced from a small sample. *Metron* 1, 3-32.
- Rahmath, S., Hema, D., Nisar, H. and Abdullah, K. (2013). Combination of TAM and TPB in Internet Banking Adoption. *International Journal of Computer Theory and Engineering*, 5(1), 146-150.
- Rakhi, T. and Mala, S. (2015). A study on the impact of consumer risk perception and innovativeness on online shopping in India. *International Journal of Retail & Distribution Management*, 43(2), 148-166
- Ren H. (2020). Research on factors influencing the willingness of high-tech enterprises to purchase science and technology insurance--a survey based on 274 high-tech enterprises in Guangzhou. *Science and Technology Progress and Countermeasures*.
- Renny, Suryo, G. and Hotniar, S. (2013). Perceived usefulness, ease of use, and attitude towards online shopping usefulness towards online airlines ticket purchase. *Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 81, 212 - 216.
- Richard J. Holden and Ben-Tzion Karsh. (2008). The Technology Acceptance Model: Its past and its future in health care. *Journal of Biomedical Informatics*, 43, 159-172.
- Riquelme, H.E. and Rios, R.E. (2010). The moderating effect of gender in the adoption of mobile banking. *The International Journal of Bank Marketing*, 28, 328-34.
- Ritu, A. and Jayesh, P. (1998). A conceptual and operational definition of personal innovativeness in the domain of information technology. *Information Systems Research*, 9(2), 101-215.
- Robert, J. V., Luc, P., Paul, D., Jean-Pierre, C. and Claude, M. (1992). Ajzen and Fishbein Theory of Reasoned Action as Applied to moral behaviour - A confirmatory analysis. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 62(1),98-109.
- Roehrich, G. (2004). Consumer innovativeness: Concepts and measurements. *Journal of Business Research*, 57(6), 671-677.
- Rogers, E. (2003). *Diffusion of Innovations* (5th ed.). New York, NY: Free Press.
- Rogers, E. M. (1983). *Diffusions of innovations*. (3rd ed.). New York: The free Press.
- Rogers, E.M. (1976). New product adoption and diffusion. *The Journal of Consumer Research*, 2, 290-301.
- Rogers, Everett M. and F.F. Shoemaker. (1971). *Communication of innovation*. New York: The Free Press.
- Roselius, R. (1971). Consumer rankings of risk reduction methods. *Journal of Marketing*, 3(1), 56-61.
- Rupak, R., Greg, R., Jei, Y. and Ben, J. (2014). Technology acceptance model (TAM) and social media usage: an empirical study on Facebook. *Journal of Enterprise Information Management*, 27(1).
- Saba, T. B., Neda, A. and Saeedeh, R. H. (2017). The effect of perceived risk on social commerce adoption based on the TAM model. *International Journal of Electronic Commerce Studies*, 8(2), 73-196.
- Said S. Al-Gahtani (2016). Empirical investigation of e-learning acceptance and assimilation: A structural equation model. *Computing and Informatics*, 12, 27-50.
- Sarstedt, M., Henseler, J., and Ringle, C. M. (2011). Multi-group analysis in partial least squares (PLS) Path Modeling: Alternative methods and empirical results. *Advances in International Marketing*, 22, 195-218.

- Scholderer, J., Balderjahn, I., Bredahl, L. and Grunert, K. G. (1999). The perceived benefits of genetically modified food products: Experts versus consumers. *European Advances in Consumer Research*, 4, 123-129.
- Shan, M.Y., Wang, X.M. & Zhang R.L.. (2015). A study of mobile commerce adoption among offline merchants based on technology acceptance model. *Guangxi Social Science*, (09), 66-71.
- Shao, T. & Yu, J.Y.. (2020). Analysis of factors influencing consumers' brand loyalty to bike-sharing. *Journal of Mudanjiang Normal College (Social Science Edition)*, (01), 43-50. doi:10.13815/j.cnki.jmtc(pss).2020.01.005.
- Shao, Y. M., Wang, Y. Q. & Liu, M. R.. (2017). A study on the impact of website characteristics on impulse buying based on technology acceptance model. *Research in Business Economics*, (23), 56-58.
- Sheng, G., Yue, B. & Gong, S. Yu.. (2019). A study of bike-sharing users' willingness to use consistently - an extended model based on TAM theory. *Journal of Northeastern University (Social Science Edition)*, (06), 567-574. doi:10.15936/j.cnki.1008-3758.2019.06.003.
- Sheng, L.J. & Xie, T.. (2019). A study on the factors influencing consumers' purchase intention of new energy vehicles. *China Business Journal*, (21), 84-87. doi:10.19699/j.cnki.issn2096-0298.2019.21.084.
- Shi, X.R. & Zhou, Y.. (2020). Study on the influencing factors of TRIZ application in agricultural industry alliance. *Journal of Liaoning University of Technology (Social Science Edition)*, (04), 33-35. doi:10.15916/j.issn1674-327x.2020.04.010.
- Shih, H. P. (2004). An empirical study on predicting user acceptance of e-shopping on the Web. *Information and Management*, 41,351-368.
- Song, B.L. & Chen, L.Y.. (2014). A cognitive model of technological knowledge acceptance - a perspective based on the technological innovation process of firms. *Science Management Research*, (06), 68-71. doi:10.19445/j.cnki.15-1103/g3.2014.06.018.
- Stephen, A. S., Ku, C. H. and Parul, A. (2018). Understanding how university student perceptions of resources affect technology acceptance in online learning courses. *Australasian Journal of Educational Technology*, 34(4).
- Stone, R. W. and Baker-Eveleth, L. (2013). Students' expectation, confirmation, and continuance intention to use electronic textbooks. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 29(3), 984-990.
- Sulaiman, A., Jaafar, N. I. and Mohezar, S. (2006). An overview of mobile banking adoption among the urban community. *International Journal of Mobile Communications*, 5(2), 157-168.
- Susan L. Holak and Donald R. Lehmann (1990). Purchase intentions and the dimensions of innovation: An exploratory model. *Journal of Product Innovation Management*, 7(1), 59-73.
- Syed, A. R., Amna, U. and Nida, S. (2017). New determinants of ease of use and perceived usefulness for mobile banking adoption. *Int. J. Electronic Customer Relationship Management*, 11(1).
- Tan, M. and Teo, T. S. (2000). Factors influencing the adoption of Internet banking. *Journal of the AIS*, 1(1es), 5.
- Tang, J. T. E., Tang, T. I. and Chiang, C.H. (2012). Blog learning: effects of users' usefulness and efficiency towards continuance intention. *Behaviour & Information Technology*, 33(1), 36-50.
- Tang, S.L. & Zhu, H.H.. (2011). A study of third-party trust mechanism for e-commerce based on technology acceptance model. *Library Intelligence Work*, (08), 140-144+53.
- Tang, Y.Q., Fan, C.R. & Tan, D.Q.. (2017). A study on the influencing factors of consumer participation in collaborative consumption in China under the sharing economy. *Soft Science*, (10), 136-139. doi:10.13956/j.ss.1001-8409.2017.10.29.
- Taylor, S. and Todd, P. (1995). Decomposition and crossover effects in the theory of planned behavior: A study of consumer adoption intentions. *International Journal of Research in Marketing*, 12(2), 137-155.
- Teo, T. S. H., Lim, V. K. G.. (1999). Intrinsic and extrinsic motivation in internet usage. *Omega*, 27(1), 25-37.
- Thambiah, S. (2013). Islamic Retail Banking Adoption in Malaysia: The moderating effect of religion and region. *International Journal of Applied Economics and Finance*, (1),1-12.
- Thambiah, S., Eze, U. C., Santhapparaj, A. J. and Arumugam, K. (2011). Customers' perception on islamic retail banking: A comparative analysis between the urban and rural regions of Malaysia. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 6 (1), 187-198.

- Torben, T. (2015). The extent to which product characteristics of new innovations influence nurses' intention to advise them. Retrieved July 2, 2015, from https://essay.utwente.nl/67411/1/Taros_BA_BMS.pdf
- Tornatzky, L.G. and Klein, K.J. (2012). Innovation characteristics and innovation adoption implementation: A meta-analysis of findings. *IEEE Transactions on Engineering Management*, 29(1), 28-45.
- Tsai, J. P. and Ho, C. F. (2013). Does design matter? Affordance perspective on smartphone usage. *Industrial Management and Data Systems*, 113(9), 1248-1269.
- Ueltschy, L. C., Krampf, R. F. and Yannopoulos, P. (2004). A cross national study of perceived consumer risk towards online (internet) purchasing. *The Multinational Business Review*, 12(2), 59-82.
- V. Venkatesh (2000). Determinants of perceived ease of use: Integrating control, intrinsic motivation, and emotion into the technology acceptance model. *Information Systems Research*, 1, 342- 365.
- Van der Heijden, H., T. Verhagen (2003). Understanding online purchase intentions: Contributions from technology and trust perspectives. *European Journal of Information Systems*, 12(1), 41-8.
- Venkatesh V,Bala H(2008).Technology acceptance model 3 and a research agenda on interventions.Decision Venkatesh V,Bala H.Technology acceptance model 3 and a research agenda on interventions. *Decision Sciences*, 39(2):273-315.
- Venkatesh, V. and Davis, F. D. (2000). A theoretical extension of the technology acceptance model: Four longitudinal field studies. *Management Science*, 46, 186-204.
- Venkatesh,V,and Davis,F.D.A(2000) Theoretical Extension of the Technology Acceptance Model:Four Longitudinal Field Studies. *Management Science*, 45(2):186- 204.
- Venkatraman, N. and Grant, J. H. (1986). Construct measurement in organizational strategy research: A critique and proposal. *Academy of Management Review*, 11(1), 71-87.
- Vijayarathy, L.R. (2004). Predicting consumer intentions to use online shopping: the case for an augmented technology acceptance model. *Information & Management*, 41(6), 747-762.
- Viswanathan, M. (2005). Measurement error and research design. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage.
- Wang, W., Ngai, E. W. T. and Wei, H. (2011). Explaining instant messaging continuance intention: The role of personality. *International Journal of Human-Computer Interaction*, 28(8), 500-510.
- Wan, J. & Kuo, H.T.. (2019). The impact of online community-related attributes on consumer trust in mobile e-commerce. *Explorations in Intelligence*, (12), 89-95.
- Wan, X.W. & Shi, Y.K.. (2012). A survey and analysis of regional medical information system satisfaction based on technology acceptance model. *Statistics and Decision Making*, (19), 119-122. doi:10.13546/j.cnki.tjyc.2012.19.028.
- Wang, B.F., Jiang, R., He, S.Y., Sun, C.C. & Hu, J.. (2020). An introduction to the demand for portable wearable devices among the elderly in the community--a case study of smart bracelets. *China Geriatric Health Medicine*, (04),21-26.
- Wang, C.Y.. (2017). Research on the application of wearable technology in the intelligent service of urban metro transportation. *Intelligent Building and Smart City*, (10), 82-83. doi:10.13655/j.cnki.ibci.2017.10.030.
- Wang, D.H.. (2018). A study on the factors influencing consumers' willingness to repeat purchase under online shopping model - based on customer value theory and the moderating effect of habit. *Research in Business Economics*, (23), 84-86.
- Wang, J. & Cheng, W.T.. (2017). Technical acceptance model construction for educational mobile applications. *Library and Intelligence Work*, (16), 60-65. doi:10.13266/j.issn.0252-3116.2017.16.009.
- Wang, J. & Deng, W.M.. (2016). A study of factors influencing the use of Internet financial products based on technology acceptance model. *Research in Business Economics*, (17), 186-188.
- Wang, M.R. & Fang, W.H.. (2020). Research on factors influencing public willingness to use Internet medical service platforms. *Journal of Beijing University of Aeronautics and Astronautics (Social Science Edition)*, (03), 150-156. doi:10.13766/j.bhsk.1008-2204.2019.0001.
- Wang, N., Wang, G. & Fang H.. (2020).Analysis of factors influencing the usage behavior of police APP in the TAM theory perspective. *Journal of Armed Police Academy*, (01), 83-91.
- Wang, R.C., Mu,Y.R., Zhu, X.F. & Zhu, Q.H.. (2019). An Empirical Study on the Influencing Factors of the Willingness to Use Library Mobile Services——A technology acceptance model based on information security perception and mobility. *Library Forum*, (06), 1-9.

- Wang, R.T. & Zhang, S.. (2019). A study on the influence of personal factors on the purchase intention of cross-border online shopping consumers - A case study of China and Thailand. *Business and Management*, (08), 115-118. doi:10.16517/j.cnki.cn12-1034/f.2019.08.028.
- Wang, X.B. & Gu, Bin. (2020). Trust-based factors influencing purchase intention of mobile social e-commerce. *China Circulation Economy*, (04), 21-31. doi:10.14089/j.cnki.cn11-3664/f.2020.04.003.
- Wang, X.J., Wan Y.H. & Cheng J.. (2019). Research on the mechanism of customer psychological contract formation based on TAM theory - an empirical study in B2C scenario. *Operations Research and Management*, (11), 116-124.
- Wanyoike, M. Daniel, Elegwa, M. and Anthony, G. W. (2013). Determinants of ICT adoption by formal small enterprises in urban Kenya. *International Journal of Arts and Commerce*, 1(7), 48-60.
- Weegels, M. F. and Kanis, H. (2000). Risk perception in consumer product use. *Accident Analysis and Prevention*, 32(2), 365-370.
- Wei, W., Xiong, Y.S., Wu, X.T., Jiang, Z.Y. & Wang, Y.H.. (2019). A study on users' willingness to use intelligent voice customer service behavior. *China Business Journal*, (05), 24-26. doi:10.19699/j.cnki.issn2096-0298.2019.05.024.
- Wei, Z.P. & Zhang, L.. (2020). Exploring the factors influencing user behavior of online audiobook platforms--an empirical study based on technology acceptance model. *Publishing and Printing*, (01), 91-97. doi:10.19619/j.issn.1007-1938.2020.01.016.
- Wen, F. & Ling, W.Q.. (2006). An explanatory model of online shopping motivation - Technology Acceptance Model. *Mall Modernization*, (19), 114.
- Wu, C.L. & Chen, X.. (2020). A study of the factors influencing the use of the "pigai.org" based on the "Technology Acceptance Model". *Heilongjiang Education (Theory and Practice)*, (02), 38-39.
- Wu, F.J.. (2019). Analysis of influencing factors of middle-aged and elderly people's application of online government services based on technology acceptance model. *Electronic Commerce*, (11), 45-48. doi:10.14011/j.cnki.dzsw.2019.11.022.
- Wu, J. H. and Wang, S. C. (2005). What drives mobile commerce? An empirical evaluation of the revised technology acceptance model. *Information & Management*, 42, 719-729.
- Wu, L., Shao, P.J., Sheng, X.D. & Ye, Q.F.. (2012). An empirical study of IoT service adoption based on an improved technology acceptance model. *Management Review*, (03), 66-74+131. doi:10.14120/j.cnki.cn11-5057/f.2012.03.001.
- Wu, Q., Chen, S. & Zhu, Q. H.. (2020). Competitive intelligence analysis of China's elderly smart wearable device industry from the perspective of industrial chain. *Intelligence Theory and Practice*, (05), 38-44+67. doi:10.16353/j.cnki.1000-7490.2020.05.006.
- Wu, Q.L. & Zhang, P.Z. (2018). A UTAUT-based E-learning user acceptance model for business schools in the context of Internet+. *Journal of Shanghai Jiaotong University*, (02), 233-241. doi:10.16183/j.cnki.jsjtu.2018.02.017.
- Wu, W.B., Li, Shuang, Xiang, Z.Q. & Zhang, M.Y.. (2019). A study on drivers' willingness to continuously use shared logistics platform - an empirical analysis of TAM model. *Economic Management*, (10), 178-193. doi: 10.19616/j.cnki.bmj.2019.10.011.
- Xia, B.G. & Chang, Y.P.. (2014). A study on the communication mechanism of government weibo - a perspective based on technology acceptance model. *Journal of the National School of Administration*, (03), 102-106. doi:10.14063/j.cnki.1008-9314.2014.03.096.
- Xiang, Y. T., Li, M. D., Tao, W. G., Li, L. & Lin, M.. (2020). Purchase intention and influencing factors of smart facilities for urban elderly. *Green Technology*, (12), 258-261. doi:10.16663/j.cnki.lskj.2020.12.095.
- Xie, L.R.. (2014). A review of the evolution of technology acceptance models. *Graduate Journal of Huazhong Normal University*, (01), 155-161.
- Xie, X.Z., An, J. & Wang, Y.. (2015). A study of WeChat users' information publishing behavior based on technology acceptance model. *Journal of Intelligence*, (08), 801-808.
- Xiong, Y. & Li, Y. (2008). An empirical study of trust in e-commerce based on technology acceptance model. *Journal of Beijing University of Technology and Business (Social Science Edition)*, (05), 36-40. doi:10.16299/j.1009-6116.2008.05.013.
- Xu Y.. (2019). The influence of user needs on the willingness to follow the public number of university library services - based on technology acceptance model. *Journal of Yancheng Normal College*

- (*Humanities and Social Sciences Edition*), (05), 89-93. doi:10.16401/j.cnki.ysxb.1003-6873.2019.05.127.
- Xu, L.L. & Zhu, J. (2018). Analysis of the impact of mobile e-commerce personalized recommendation on consumers' purchase intention. *Research in Business Economics*, (06), 54-57.
- Xu, Q.Q. & Wu, Q. (2019). Analysis of factors influencing elderly users' use of smart washing machines. *Information Technology and Informatization*, (03), 144-146.
- Xu, S. & Tian, X.X.. (2020). Research on factors influencing users' willingness to use TAM-based online learning platform. *China Education Informatization*, (08), 78-85.
- Xu, S. H. & Lei, G. Q.. (2019). Purchase intentions and influencing factors of middle-aged groups in small and medium-sized cities regarding corporate elderly care services. *Science and Management*, (04), 43-49.
- Xu, X.D. & He, D.D.. (2019). An empirical study of factors influencing library mobile service usage intention - A technology acceptance model based on variables such as information security perception and mobility. *Library*, (02), 79-85.
- Xu, Y. (2019). A study on the factors influencing consumers' QR code scanning behavior. *Times Finance*, (14), 117-118.
- Yang, H.Y. & Zhou, M.J.. (2019). Analysis of factors influencing e-commerce shopping based on ATM model. *Business Economics*, (11),40-43.
- Yang, J.L. & Zhao, J.W.. (2018). A study on the evaluation of library OPAC functions from the perspective of user information behavior. *New Century Library*, (03), 59-63. doi:10.16810/j.cnki.1672-514X.2018.03.013.
- Yang, K. C. C. (2005). Exploring factors affecting the adoption of mobile commerce in Singapore. *Telematics and Informatics*, 22(3), 257-277.
- Yang, Y. W., Sun, G. F. & Wang, Y.. (2016). Are consumers willing to adopt recommendations? --Based on Information System Success-Technology Acceptance Model. *Journal of Central University of Finance and Economics*, (07), 109-117.
- Yang, Y.F. & Li, G.J.. (2012). A study of TAM3-based technology acceptance model for digital library users. *Library Intelligence Research*, (03), 15-24.
- Yang, Y.K.. (2017).An empirical study of factors influencing knowledge sharing behavior of MOOC platform users - based on Schmitt's strategic experience module and TAM model. *Journal of Information Resource Management*, (04), 66-74. doi:10.13365/j.jirm.2017.04.066.
- Ye, X. C.. (2020). Research on cultivation strategy of core competitiveness of real estate enterprises based on customer value theory. *Times Economic and Trade*, (01), 74-75. doi:10.19463/j.cnki.sdjm.2020.01.031.
- Yeh, R. K. and Teng, T. C. (2012). Extended conceptualisation of perceived usefulness: empirical test in the context of information system use continuance. *Behaviour & Information Technology*. 31(5).
- Yi, M. Y., Kirk, D. F. and Park, J. S. (2006). Understanding the role of individual innovativeness in the acceptance of it-based innovations: Comparative analyses of models and measures. *Decision Sciences*, 37,393-426.
- Yin, W. L.. (2017). A study of rural e-commerce user acceptance model. *China Business Journal*, (34), 16-19. doi:10.19699/j.cnki.issn2096-0298.2017.34.009.
- Yu, C.P., Zhang, Z.G. & Lin, C.P.. (2019). A study on the mechanism of enterprise management innovation process based on technology acceptance model. *Scientific Research Management*, (08), 206-214. doi:10.19571/j.cnki.1000-2995.2019.08.021.
- Yu, Y. & Chen, W.S.. (2017). A review of research on factors influencing consumers' online purchase intention. *Research in Business Economics*, (16), 46-49.
- Yu, Y.H., Song, J. & Yu, J.. (2018). Analysis of factors influencing the usage intention unmanned supermarkets based on TAM model. *China Market*, (28), 115-116. doi:10.13939/j.cnki.zgsc.2018.28.115.
- Yuan, H.S. & Zhao, K.. (2011). A study on the model of information technology acceptance behavior in knowledge alliances. *Library and Intelligence Work*, (02), 68-71+36.
- Yuan, X. & Wang, A.M.. (2018). Research on factors influencing willingness to use shared cars based on TAM. *Journal of Wuhan University of Technology (Information and Management Engineering Edition)*, (04), 434-438.

- Zhang P.. (2017). Theoretical evolution and research development of technology acceptance models. *Intelligence Science*, (09), 165-171. doi:10.13833/j.cnki.is.2017.09.027.
- Zhang, H., Xiao, R. X., Wang, Y. N. & Fan, F. W.. (2015). A study on TPACK development of teacher-training students based on technology acceptance model. *China Electrochemical Education*, (05), 111-117.
- Zhang, J.H., Wang, J.P. & Chen, Y.N.. (2020). Research on consumer dissatisfaction of sports protection smart wearable devices. *Journal of Zhejiang Textile and Clothing Vocational and Technical College*, (02), 15-20+25.
- Zhang, L.Y. & Zhang, R. (2015). Antecedent analysis of key variables of technology acceptance model (TAM). *Journal of Information Resource Management*, (02), 11-20. doi:10.13365/j.jirm.2015.02.011.
- Zhang, N. Guo, X.H. & Chen G.Q.. (2007). The initial acceptance extension model of information technology and its empirical study. *Systems Engineering Theory and Practice*, (09), 123-130.
- Zhang, N., Guo, X. and Chen, G., (2008). IDT-TAM integrated model for IT adoption. *Tsinghua Science and Technology*, 13(3), 306-311.
- Zhang, T. R., Tao, D., Qua, X. D., Zhang, X. Y., Lin, R. and Zhang, W. (2017). The roles of initial trust and perceived risk in public's acceptance of automated vehicles. *Transportation Research, Part C* 98, 207-220.
- Zhang, T., Zhang, Y. & Zhang, W.K. (2020). Research on ETC users' usage behavior based on technology acceptance model. *Highway Traffic Technology*, (07), 122-128.
- Zhang, W., Yang, T. & Zhang, W.K.. (2020). A study on the mechanism of mobile shopping contextual factors on impulsive purchase intention. *Management Review*, (02), 174-183. doi:10.14120/j.cnki.cn11-5057/f.2020.02.014.
- Zhang, Y., Wan, G., Huang, L. and Yao, Q. (2015), Study on the impact of perceived network externalities on consumers' new product purchase intention. *Journal of Service Science and Management*, 8(1), 99-106.
- Zhang, Y.,Zheng, L. & Liu, H.. (2018). An empirical study of mobile reading app users' adoption behavior. *Library Theory and Practice*, (02), 97-100+107. doi:10.14064/j.cnki.issn1005-8214.2018.02.022.
- Zhao, K. & Zhang, J.Q.. (2010). An empirical study of the technology acceptance model TAM in the evaluation selection of teaching software. *China Education Informatization*, (05), 75-77.
- Zhao, K.. (2007). Analysis of the current situation and outlook of information technology user acceptance model research. *Journal of Yunnan University of Finance and Economics*, (02), 104-108. doi:10.16537/j.cnki.jynufe.2007.02.020.
- Zhao, K.. (2007). Analysis of the current status of research on technology acceptance models for complex systems and prospects. *Shanghai Management Science*, (02), 44-46.
- Zhao, L.L., Zhao, K.Y., Hou, L.X. & Xu, J.. (2015). A study on teachers' TPACK competence development from the perspective of technology acceptance model. *Educational Theory and Practice*, (11), 25-27.
- Zhao, X.Q. & Wang, S.C.. (2019). Exploring the influencing factors of WeChat applet users' willingness to use consistently. *Modern Intelligence*, (06), 70-80+90.
- Zhao, Y., Sun, X.S., Li, T. & Mao, X.. (2020). Analysis of smart wearable devices market and new technology development trend. *Science and Technology Economic Journal*, (19), 16-17.
- Zhao, Z.F. & Jin, L.. (2019). A study on user satisfaction and its influencing factors of mobile government service platform based on TAM model. *Administrative Science Forum*. (06), 34-39.
- Zheng, C.L. & Zhang, Q.T.. (2020). A study of WeChat knowledge sharing behavior based on TPB and TAM models. *New Century Library*, (04), 62-68. doi:10.16810/j.cnki.1672-514X.2020.04.011.
- Zhou Y. S., Tang S. H. & Xiao J.. (2016). A study of consumers' purchase intention on live e-commerce platform - based on social presence perspective. *Contemporary Economic Management*.
- Zhou, P., Fu,S.Y. & Zhao,Y.C.. (2020). An empirical study on the factors influencing the continuous use of shopping app users. *Nanjing Normal University Journal (Natural Science Edition)*, (02), 140-148.
- Zhu, F. & Hu, J.W.. (2018). A review of theories and influencing factors of cross-border e-commerce consumers' purchase intention. *Modern Business Industry*, (24), 24-27. doi:10.19311/j.cnki.1672-3198.2018.24.010.

- Zhu, S. E., Zheng, H. L., Zhu, H. R. & Song, P. H.. (2019). A study on the mechanism of impact of smart medical system usage on patients' satisfaction with medical care - A perspective based on technology acceptance model. *Chinese Hospital Management*, (10),61-64.
- Zhu, Z.H. & Yuan, Q.J.. (2018). Technology acceptance model and its application and prospect in information system research. *Intelligence Science*, (12), 168-176. doi:10.13833/j.issn.1007-7634.2018.12.031.

Cite this article:

Chen Wei (2021). The influence of Consumers' Purchase intention on Smart Wearable Device: A study of Consumers in East China. *International Journal of Science and Business*, 5(8), 46-72. doi: <https://doi.org/0.5281/zenodo.4765601>

Retrieved from <http://ijsab.com/wp-content/uploads/784.pdf>

Published by

